

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>SEE test of GaN HEMT power devices under dynamic biasing conditions</i>
Project TA identifier <i>Example: TA1-11 (1st TA call, experiment 11)</i>	TA2-01
General application (e.g. space, high-reliability ground level, avionic, high-energy accelerators and others)	<i>Testing methods for GaN-FET device</i>
Type of test (e.g. SEE, TID, TNID, radiation monitor calibration and others)	SEE
Group leader, Institute	JB Sauveplane, CNES
Date(s) of the experiment	1-2/06/22
Facility	UCL
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	12

Objectives of the experiments

The aim of the project is to perform heavy ion test on commercial GaN-HEMT power devices under dynamic/switching conditions.

GaN devices have the unique ability to switch from OFF to ON state in a few nano second. This property may impact the robustness against heavy ion. The main idea of the study is to verify if the safe operating area obtained in static biasing condition is the same as the one obtained in dynamic condition.

The heavy ion test campaign was done in 2 step:

- Firstly, to obtain the safe operating area in static biasing condition under normal incidence and in tilted/rolled incidence
- Secondly to obtain the safe operating area in dynamic biasing condition

Experiment test report

The full test results are summarized in the excel file "CNES-SEE-GaN-results-UCL-week 22-2022" included in PDF annex.

Below is a brief summary of the results:

1-Test vehicle preparation:

We have tested the following devices:

- EPC 2152 (half bridge with integrated driver, VDS max 70V, size 3.9 x 2.6mm², GEN7)
- EPC 2104 (half bridge, VDS max 100V, size 6.05 x 2.3mm², GEN 5, Ron-sp=35mΩ.mm²)
- EPC 2102 (half bridge, VDS max 60V, size 6.05 x 2.3mm², GEN 5, Ron-sp=25mΩ.mm²)
- EPC 2010C (single, VDS max 200V, size 3.6 x 1.6mm², GEN 4, Ron-sp=104mΩ.mm²)
- EPC 2215 (single, VDS max 200V, size 4.6 x 1.6mm², GEN 6, Ron-sp=44mΩ.mm²)
- GaN System GS66516T (single, VDS max 650V, size 9 x 7.6 mm²)
- Panasonic PGA26E19BA (single, VDS max 600V, size 7.9 x 7.9 mm²)

All devices except PGA26E19BA were backside thinned down to 45µm to allow heavy ion to reach the sensitive region. We have tried to obtain even thinner devices but they were too fragile. Due to this limitation, we have chosen Rhodium ion (range 88µm, LET 45.8 MeV/mg/cm²) but even with this ion, we are limit to 45° tilt except for the PGA device that has a classical plastic opening preparation. Therefore, for this last reference, we have been able to tilt up to 75°.

2- Electrical validation of dynamic test bench

Dynamic test bench have been validated under representative condition in CNES (devices under vacuum) and we have noticed that:

- Switching time were too slow (around 1-2µs) because of parasitic capacitance in coaxial cable between test vehicle inside chamber and equipment + driver outside chamber.
- At 100kHz switching frequency temperature reached by GaN-FET were above 150°C for GS66516T and EPC2034C

Consequently, test bench set up has been optimized to improve switching time and testing frequency has been limited to 10kHz for some devices to avoid failure due to overheating.

3-Test results:

Static result:

- EPC2010C (VDS max 200): Vpass= 220V, Vfail=250V, No influence of tilt up to 45°
- EPC2215 (VDS max 200): Vpass= 150V, Vfail=160V, Tilt not tested
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These results indicate that the oldest generation of EPC devices are more robust to SEE compared to the newest one. Device shrink that increases electric field in drain to source region can explain it.

- GS66516T (VDS max 650V): Vpass= 400V, Vfail=425V, No influence of tilt up to 45°
- PGA26E19BA (VDS max 600V):
 - o Vpass= 400V, Vfail=425V, Tilt 0°
 - o Vpass= 350V, Roll 75°
 - o **No Vpass @ Tilt 70°**

This is the most interesting result we get. Depending on the position of device in the irradiation chamber (see below test plateau inside vacuum chamber), the influence of tilt was not the same. When ion strike device in direction 1 (perpendicular to interdigitate fingers) we have not been able to obtain a Vpass even at 200V. But when ion strike in direction 2 (parallel to finger) device has the same robustness as in normal incidence. This result seems to indicate that normal incidence is not the worst case configuration for testing contrary to MOSFET. A high tilt with ion strike direction perpendicular to fingers seems to be the worst case. This results need to be confirmed on other GaN-FET references but it would not be so surprising as the electric in GaN-FET device is lateral contrary to MOSFET where it is vertical.

Direction1:
Perpendicular to fingers

Direction2: // to fingers

Dynamic results:

We have not seen a huge difference between static and dynamic test results everything else being equal. We can notice that Vpass obtained under dynamic condition were always slightly higher compare to Vpass obtained in static condition. This observation is especially true for GS66516T on which we have obtained a Vpass at 500V in dynamic condition and the next run few minutes after on the same part in static condition we have obtained an immediate breakdown at 500V. This can be explained by GaN channel temperature that was estimated to be around 150°C for this reference during dynamic test whereas it was below 40°C in static condition. Consequently we can say that dV/dt up to around 4V/ns during switching has no influence on SEE robustness contrary to temperature that increases device robustness to SEE. This behavior is line with observation already made on MOSFET and may come from efficiency of impact ionization phenomena that decreases when temperature increases.

Wave form during testing on PGA26E19BA (VDS 350V, 100kHz, I_{max} 650mA)

Main conclusion:

- Newest generation of EPC GaN-FET are much more sensitive to SEE compared to previous ones.
- Dynamic testing condition is not worst case compared to static condition
- Highly tilted condition with ion strike direction perpendicular to interdigitated fingers seems to be a very sensitive testing condition giving SOA at least twice lower (and maybe even more) compared to normal incidence.

This last result need to be confirmed on EPC and GaN system reference but due to the limited range of ion in highly tilted configuration we need to define alternative approach for testing these devices (by changing device preparation technic and/or by using a facility with a more energetic ion).

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication X (Radecs 2023)
Data for Thesis
Follow-up experiment at same facility
Follow-up experiment at another facility X
Other

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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